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Neuropsychiatry

Why treating emotional stress with tranquilizers is a must

Abstract

As emotions are still classified as non-biological events by many practitioners, patients die unnecessarily. It is of great importance to prescribe existing aids such as tranquilizers more courageously.

When emotions are lethal

The loss of a loved one can literally break a person's heart. This is especially true for patients with pre-existing heart chronic heart failure. This group of patients has a significant risk of dying from the biological correlate of their feelings when they experience grief and - it can be assumed - other emotional stresses of a considerable nature. Basically, this has been known to every internist, cardiologist, neurologist and neuropsychiatrist for a long time. However, it

has now been confirmed once again by a study from Sweden.¹

That emotions can throw a heart out of balance is known to the wider medical community from Takotsubo syndrome.² Under the influence of catecholamines, stress hormones and resulting autoimmune inflammatory reactions, a disturbance of the left ventricle of the heart can result which has all the signs of a heart attack, except that the coronary arteries are usually without any pathological abnormalities. Most, though not all, patients with Takotsubo "broken heart"

syndrome recover from this quite dangerous "stress disorder" after a while.³ Thus, for patients with chronic heart failure, sudden and intense, but also low-level chronic emotional stress can lead to death in this patient collective. Krisztina Laszlo from the Karolinska Institute and her team were able to substantiate this knowledge thanks to an evaluation of the national Swedish register "RiksSvikt". This very Swedish (transparent) database contains information about almost half a million Swedish residents who have suffered from chronic heart failure since 1987. Lazlo was able to determine whether the patients had lost a relative during this time by comparing the data with the Swedish death register.

The analysis showed that the loss of a relative was associated with an increased risk of cardiac death. The risk was - in parts - higher the closer the person was to the patient, i.e. the greater the emotional stress. After the loss of a spouse, the risk of death increased by one-fifth and after the death of a sister or brother by about 13%. To everyone's surprise, the death of one's own child increased the risk of cardiac mortality by only 10%, and the death of a grandchild by 5%. The death of a parent had no effect at all. Obviously, the mind provoking hypothesis put forward by some psychotherapists and/or psychiatrist's is correct that mammals, possibly even almost all emotion-competent creatures, become more resilient to stress in these cases through as yet unknown mechanisms, with the aim of preserving the survival of the species by means of as yet unexplored metabolic changes.⁶ The same is true for some fringe scientists who are looking at this issue from their very own angle such as the interaction of faith and wellbeing.⁵

The risk of dying was highest in the first week (78%), especially in the case of the loss of a spouse (113%). For the death of one's own child by some 30%. These figures also correspond to the amount of stress hormones and inflammatory mediators over the time axis. Author Laszlo suspects that grief activates the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, which leads to an increased release of stress hormones that attack the patients' weakened heart. In psychoneuroimmunology,

this has been considered a fact for a long time. A reaction in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system and in the sympathetic nervous system is also possible, according to the Swedish study. This fact is equally not surprising. Because in this case, too, there can occur an additional cascade of stress hormones and inflammatory reactions that the patient's heart cannot compensate for.⁴

Although the results of the Laszlo study are not groundbreaking, it is of considerable importance because it rests on a solid data base that has been correctly evaluated.

Clinical consequence

Clinically, it is important to treat people with heart disease in emotional emergencies, but also in chronic stress states, not just with psychotherapy (which might be a help, not a cure) but also with strong tranquilizers, nonselective beta-blockers (like propranolol) and mild anti-inflammatory drugs.

Remember

Emotions are not just feelings. They have very powerful biological correlates with lethal effects.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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Sources

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